

Classification of Uncertainty in Descriptive Data Representing Scientific Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

Through constant research the amount of gained knowledge grows rapidly. In this process often questions remain unanswered or the answers obtained are contradictory, imprecise or subject to a low level of certainty. Such imperfect knowledge is considered as uncertain. In order to transfer scientific knowledge into data, inherent uncertainties need to be expressed explicitly and thus at first be classified. Based on a literature survey and qualitative expert interviews, we propose a new generic approach to classifying uncertainty in scientific knowledge according to the nature of the underlying imperfect knowledge.

1 INTRODUCTION

Research aims to generate new scientific knowledge by exploring the unknown. It is often driven by debates based on conflicting evidence, theories and interpretations. Due to these circumstances, uncertainty is an inherent part of research. Uncertainty can occur with regard to past, present and future events.

The current state of research concerning one or multiple related phenomena may be captured in data to preserve it in a structured form and make it accessible to a broad community. An example is cultural heritage data, which describes the state of research regarding physical objects of material culture, including details such as their context of creation. We regard such *descriptive data that represents scientific knowledge* as a subset of *research data*, which encompasses “any data that is generated in the course of scientific work” [3]. To ensure high data quality, the uncertainties inherent in scientific knowledge must be expressed explicitly. We plan to develop generic quality assessment and improvement methods with regard to uncertainty for such research data. One of our goals is to develop methods for explicitly modelling uncertainty in this context. As a starting point this requires a comprehensive and domain-independent *classification of uncertainty*. It should clearly define and distinguish fine-grained types of uncertainty according to the *nature of the imperfect knowledge* that is present and abstract from causes and consequences of uncertainty.

In the literature several classifications of uncertainty are presented. However, we could not find a classification that satisfies the above requirements. Existing approaches are often domain-specific [2, 4, 14, 15]. Some approaches classify uncertainty according to its cause [6, 12, 16]. Others lack clear definition and differentiation of fine-grained types of uncertainty [7, 9, 10, 12]. None of the mentioned classifications allowed us to clearly assign every case of uncertainty that we identified during our research to a class.

We propose a new stringent approach to classifying uncertainty according to the *nature of the underlying imperfect knowledge*. The approach is presented in detail in the following section. It adopts,

brings together and differentiates some of the various types of uncertainty described in the literature. We explore types of uncertainty inherent in scientific knowledge that is mapped to data. This is referred to as *intrinsic* uncertainty by Souza et al. [12]. We do not consider *extrinsic* uncertainty, which is introduced through data input or the technology used. The literature further differentiates between *epistemic* uncertainty, which “results from a lack of knowledge” [13] but can be reduced by gathering more information, and *aleatory* uncertainty, which “exists due to the random nature of physical events” [13] and thus is irreducible. Our classification abstracts from this aspect since imperfect knowledge underlying epistemic uncertainty may take the same forms as that underlying aleatory uncertainty. Therefore, each type of uncertainty presented in the following section can occur for both epistemic and aleatory uncertainty.

Besides this top-down approach based on types of uncertainty presented in the literature, we performed a bottom-up approach. We conducted 6 qualitative interviews and a workshop with 19 domain experts that perform acquisition, modelling, management and usage of various kinds of cultural heritage data (e.g. data on technical objects or artworks) to investigate the following question: *What uncertainties occur in cultural heritage data?* The domain experts discussed examples of uncertainty in cultural heritage research and typical struggles in mapping this imperfect knowledge to data. We incorporated the findings concerning types of imperfect knowledge into our classification of uncertainty. We will use some of the examples to illustrate the types of uncertainty in the following section.

2 CLASSIFICATION OF UNCERTAINTY

In the literature, uncertainty is often defined as a “lack of knowledge” [1, 4, 6, 8] or “imperfect information” [8, 9]. As a basis for our classification of uncertainty, we propose the following definition: *uncertainty is a situation in which one has imperfect knowledge about which state of nature has occurred or will occur*. This definition is inspired by the definitions of uncertainty by Anderson et al. [1] cited by Lipshitz et al. [5]. In the following, we will define several disjoint subtypes of uncertainty according to the nature of imperfect knowledge about which state of nature has occurred or will occur. Each of these types may occur for both discrete or continuous domains.

We assume that the truth is represented by *exactly one* state of nature, which we will refer to as the “true” state in the following. Depending on the research question, several dependent information aspects may be considered in combination, such as the creator(s) and creation date of an artwork. Each state of nature consists of one

Figure 1: Classification of Uncertainty

or possibly several specific values per information aspect considered. Hence, in the example each state consists of one or multiple collaborating artists and a single creation date.

In the following we will present our classification of uncertainty. It is depicted in a condensed form in Fig. 1.

2.1 Absence

In the worst case, there is complete *absence* of any knowledge concerning the true state of nature concerning a specific research question. There is no evidence for any state to be more plausible than any other or for any state to be impossible. For example, the creator of an artwork may be completely unknown.

2.2 Doubtfulness

We define *doubtfulness* as a situation in which there is an increased but limited confidence in the *occurrence of one specific state* of nature or in the *correctness of a discrepant or imprecise statement*. Doubtfulness concerning discrepant and imprecise statements will be discussed in detail in the following sections. Doubtfulness is often related to the reliability of the source of information [9], credibility [13], trust [8] and belief [16]. It results from a lack of clear evidence and is based on indications. The discussions with domain experts revealed that this type of uncertainty plays an important role, especially in cultural heritage research, since in historical sciences knowledge about the past is based on the interpretation of available sources. An example is the attribution of the painting “Salvator Mundi” to the Italian Renaissance artist Leonardo da Vinci.

2.3 Discrepancy

As *discrepancy* we denote situations in which a *discontinuous set of multiple distinct states* is known that *definitely* contains the true state. The set of alternatives actually may not just contain states directly but can also contain *imprecise statements* defined through continuous sets of states. This scenario will be discussed in the following section. In some cases it may *not* be for sure that the true state *definitely* lies within the continuous set of states. Instead, there is just an increased confidence. We view such cases as *combinations of discrepancy and doubtfulness*, i.e. doubtfulness concerning discrepant statements. In general, discrepancy may result from information that is conflicting or subject to multiple interpretations. For example, it may occur due to research debates based on different opinions by different experts, e.g. concerning the true creator of an artwork. Ambiguous statements are a source of discrepancy as they allow multiple distinct interpretations due to a lack of context [16].

Examples are historic or polysemic place names [15] and words that have more than one meaning [6]. Lovell [6] refers to ambiguity as *qualitative uncertainty* and *uncertainty in kind* as “the options differ qualitatively, not only quantitatively”. A special case of discrepancy consists in “negative information” [7], i.e. a situation in which it is known that *one specific state* has *not* occurred or will not occur.

2.4 Imprecision

Imprecision corresponds to a lack of detail and a coarse granularity. It is present if a *continuous set of multiple states* is known that *definitely* contains the true state. In contrast to discrepancy, the states within the set are *coherent* according to some sort of *similarity assessment*, such as the spatial distance for geospatial information. As discussed for discrepancy, *combinations with doubtfulness* are possible, i.e. situations in which there is only an increased but limited confidence that the set contains the true state. As mentioned earlier, there may also occur *combinations of discrepancy and imprecision*: the set of alternatives that underlies discrepancy may contain imprecise statements defined through continuous sets of states. For example, one expert may argue that an artwork has been created between 1900 and 1910, whereas another expert may argue that it must have been created in 1950. We further split *imprecision* according to whether the *boundaries* of the continuous set of states are clear or vague.

Non-specificity allows a clear differentiation between the states within the continuous set of states and those outside. Smets et al. [9] point out that this form of imprecision is decidable. The continuous set is often defined directly or indirectly through its boundaries. An example is the knowledge that an artist must have been born in Germany *between 1900 and 1910*.

Fuzziness is imprecision with “a lack of fine-graded distinctions or boundaries” [4]. It is also often referred to as *vagueness*, which is said to have borderline cases [11]. The continuous set of states may, for example, be given via a specific (perhaps itself imprecise) state in combination with a vague variance. For example, there may be indications saying that an artist has been born *around 1905 near Berlin*. Lovell [6] refers to fuzziness as *quantitative uncertainty* and *uncertainty in degree*. He gives examples of terms pertaining to degree or amount that have a fuzzy meaning, such as “old”, and thus also imply a continuous set of states with vague boundaries.

3 CONCLUSION

We presented a new approach to classifying uncertainty in scientific knowledge. It overcomes weaknesses by existing classifications concerning the requirements mentioned in Section 1 and covers the uncertainties in cultural heritage data discussed by the interviewed domain experts.

Concerning the discussion at the workshop, we are interested in learning about the similarities and differences in the perception of uncertainty by participants who look at uncertainty from different perspectives. Eventually, we want to find out how far our approach is applicable in other domains.

The presented classification of uncertainty will serve as a basis for our future work on research data quality assessment and improvement methods focusing on uncertainty.

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